

where α_i and β_j are the roots of $f(x)$ and $g(x)$, respectively, in some extension of F , each repeated according to its multiplicity. This property is often taken as the definition of the resultant.

(ii) f and g have a common root in some extension of F if and only if $R(f, g) = 0$.

(iii) $R(f, g) = (-1)^{nm} R(g, f)$.

(iv) $R(fh, g) = R(f, g) R(h, g)$ and $R(f, gh) = R(f, g) R(f, h)$.

(v) If $g = vf + h$ and $\deg(h) = d$, then $R(f, g) = a_n^{m-d} R(f, h)$.

(vi) If p is a positive integer, then $R(f(x^p), g(x^p)) = R(f(x), g(x))^p$.

All these properties are well-known [1, 7]. More details concerning the resultant can be found in [3, 4]. Another important classical result is (see [4]):

Lemma 1. *Let $f = \sum_{i=0}^n a_i x^i$ and $g = \sum_{j=0}^m b_j x^j$ be two polynomials of degrees n and m , respectively. Let, for $k \geq 0$, $r_k(x) = r_{k,n-1} x^{n-1} + \dots + r_{k,0}$ be the remainder of $x^k g(x)$ modulo $f(x)$, i.e., $x^k g(x) = v_k(x) f(x) + r_k(x)$, where v_k is some polynomial and $\deg(r_k) \leq n - 1$. Then*

$$R(f, g) = a_n^m \begin{vmatrix} r_{n-1,n-1} & r_{n-1,n-2} & \cdots & r_{n-1,0} \\ r_{n-2,n-1} & r_{n-2,n-2} & \cdots & r_{n-2,0} \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ r_{0,n-1} & r_{0,n-2} & \cdots & r_{0,0} \end{vmatrix}. \tag{2}$$

In the next section we prove a theorem on the relationship between the number of solutions of the congruence system $f(x) \equiv g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ and the resultant of two polynomials $R(f(x), g(x))$. Then using this result we give new proofs of some congruences involving the Lucas sequences.

2. Properties of the Resultant

A polynomial $f(x)$ with integer coefficients is called *not identically zero in \mathbb{Z}_q* if at least one of its coefficients is not divisible by q . Let $A = (a_{i,j})$ be an arbitrary matrix. Then by $A^{<q>}$ we will denote the matrix $(a'_{i,j})$ over \mathbb{Z}_q of the same type such that $a'_{i,j}$ is the residue of $a_{i,j}$ modulo q .

Theorem 1. *Let q be a prime and $f(x), g(x)$ be polynomials with integer coefficients that are not identically zero in \mathbb{Z}_q . If the system of congruences $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ and $g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has ℓ solutions, then $R(f(x), g(x)) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^\ell}$.*

Proof. Let $\deg f = n$ and $\deg g = m$. Then we have that the system $f(x) \equiv g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has ℓ solutions by the theorem conditions and $\ell \leq \min[n, m]$ as the polynomials are not identically zero in \mathbb{Z}_q . Let $r_k(x) = r_{k,n-1}x^{n-1} + \dots + r_{k,0}$ be the remainder of $x^k g(x)$ modulo $f(x)$, i.e., $x^k g(x) = v_k(x)f(x) + r_k(x)$, where $v_k(x)$ is some polynomial and $\deg(r_k) \leq n - 1$. Then we get the system of congruences

$$\begin{pmatrix} r_{n-1,n-1} & r_{n-1,n-2} & \cdots & r_{n-1,0} \\ r_{n-2,n-1} & r_{n-2,n-2} & \cdots & r_{n-2,0} \\ \vdots & & & \vdots \\ r_{0,n-1} & r_{0,n-2} & \cdots & r_{0,0} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x^{n-1} \\ x^{n-2} \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \pmod{q}. \tag{3}$$

This system has at least ℓ solutions, since each congruence of (3) is derived from $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ and $g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. Let $A = (a_{i,j})$ be a matrix of the system (3). With the help of the procedure analogous to row reduction using operations of swapping the rows and adding a multiple of one row to another row, we can reduce A to a matrix A_1 with integer coefficients such that $\det(A) = \pm \det(A_1)$ and $A_1^{<q>}$ is an upper triangular matrix. We can see that each solution of the system (3) is also a solution of the following system over \mathbb{Z}_q :

$$(A_1^{<q>}) \begin{pmatrix} x^{n-1} \\ x^{n-2} \\ \vdots \\ 1 \end{pmatrix} \equiv \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{pmatrix} \pmod{q}, \tag{4}$$

so (4) has at least ℓ solutions. Note that the last ℓ congruences of (4) have degrees less than ℓ . On the other hand, these congruences have at least ℓ solutions. Hence all these congruences must be congruences with zero coefficients, i.e., the last ℓ rows of $A_1^{<q>}$ are zero rows. Therefore, all elements of the last ℓ rows of A_1 are divisible by q , so $\det(A) = \pm \det(A_1)$ is divisible by q^ℓ . Thus, by Lemma 1 we have $R(f, g) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^\ell}$. \square

Remark. If one or both polynomials equal zero in \mathbb{Z}_q , then by property (i) we obtain that either $R(f, g) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^n}$ or $R(f, g) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^m}$. We do not consider this trivial case in Theorem 1.

Example. Let $f(x) = x^6 + 1$, $g(x) = (x + 1)^6 + 1$. The system of congruences $x^6 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{13}$ and $(x + 1)^6 + 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{13}$ has three solution in \mathbb{Z}_{13} : $x = 5, 6, 7$. The matrix of the system (3) for these polynomials is:

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & -6 & -15 & -20 & -15 & -6 \\ 6 & 1 & -6 & -15 & -20 & -15 \\ 15 & 6 & 1 & -6 & -15 & -20 \\ 20 & 15 & 6 & 1 & -6 & -15 \\ 15 & 20 & 15 & 6 & 1 & -6 \\ 6 & 15 & 20 & 15 & 6 & 1 \end{pmatrix}. \tag{5}$$

Since the resulting echelon form of matrices after row reduction is not unique, we obtain the reduced row echelon form of the matrix A , which is unique:

$$A_1^{<13>} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 7 & 11 & 6 & 11 & 7 \\ 0 & 1 & 9 & 11 & 1 & 11 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 8 & 3 & 11 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \longrightarrow \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 & 7 & 4 & 8 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 4 & 0 & 3 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 8 & 3 & 11 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (6)$$

So we get $\det A \equiv 0 \pmod{13^3}$ and $R(x^6 + 1, (x + 1)^6 + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{13^3}$. This resultant is actually equal to $2^4 \times 5 \times 13^3$.

Corollary 1. *Let q be a prime and $f(x), g(x)$ be polynomials of degrees n and m , respectively, with integer coefficients that are not identically zero in \mathbb{Z}_q . Let A be a matrix of the system (3) for $f(x), g(x)$. If $\text{Rank } A = p$ in \mathbb{Z}_q , then $R(f, g) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^{n-p}}$. If the system $f(x) \equiv g(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has ℓ solutions, then $n - p \geq \ell$. Moreover, if M is any $k \times k$ minor of the matrix A and $k > p$, then $M \equiv 0 \pmod{q^{k-p}}$.*

Proof. This follows from Theorem 1. □

The question about the relation of the multiplicity of q as a factor of $R(f, g)$ and the degree of common factor of the polynomials f and g modulo q was studied in [2]. This question is closely related to Theorem 1 and first appeared in [5].

3. The Congruences Involving the Terms of the Lucas Sequences

Theorem 2. *Let $f(x) = a_n x^n + \dots + a_0$ be a polynomial of degree n with integer coefficients and q be an odd prime. Let $a_0 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ and let the congruence $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ have ℓ solutions. Then*

$$R(f(x), x^{q-1} - 1) \equiv a_n^{q-1} \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^{q-1} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^\ell}, \quad (7)$$

where α_i are the roots of $f(x)$, each repeated according to its multiplicity.

Proof. Consider $R(f(x), x^{q-1} - 1)$. Since $f(x) = a_n \prod_{i=1}^n (x - \alpha_i)$, then

$$R(f(x), x^{q-1} - 1) = a_n^{q-1} \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^{q-1} - 1). \quad (8)$$

We know that q is an odd prime, so the congruence $x^{q-1} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has $q - 1$ solutions (zero is not one of them). On the other hand, the congruence

$f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has ℓ nonzero solutions, as $a_0 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. Hence the system of congruences $f(x) \equiv x^{q-1} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ also has ℓ solutions. Then by Theorem 1 we have $R(f(x), x^{q-1} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^\ell}$. \square

Theorem 3. *Let $f(x) = a_n x^n + \dots + a_0$ be a polynomial of degree n with integer coefficients and q be an odd prime. Let $a_0 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ and let the congruence $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ have ℓ solutions. If b solutions of them are quadratic residues modulo q , then*

$$R(f(x), x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1) \equiv a_n^{\frac{q-1}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^b} \tag{9}$$

and

$$R(f(x), x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1) \equiv a_n^{\frac{q-1}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^{\ell-b}}, \tag{10}$$

where α_i are the roots of $f(x)$, each repeated according to its multiplicity.

Proof. Consider $R(f(x), x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1)$. Since $f(x) = a_n \prod_{i=1}^n (x - \alpha_i)$, then

$$R\left(f(x), x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1\right) = a_n^{\frac{q-1}{2}} \prod_{i=1}^n (\alpha_i^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1). \tag{11}$$

We know that $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has b nonzero solutions which are quadratic residues modulo q . Hence the system of congruences $f(x) \equiv x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has b solutions. Then by Theorem 1 we have $R(f(x), x^{q-1} - 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^b}$. Since $\ell - b$ solutions of $f(x) \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ are quadratic nonresidues modulo q , then by analogy we prove that $R(f(x), x^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^{\ell-b}}$. \square

As an illustration of applications of Theorem 1 we consider the following theorem.

Theorem 4. *Let q be an odd prime and P, Q be any integers such that $Q \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. If the Legendre symbol $\left(\frac{P^2-4Q}{q}\right)$ is equal to 1, then*

$$V_{q-1}(P, Q) \equiv Q^{q-1} + 1 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{12}$$

$$V_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2(P, Q) \equiv \left(Q^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1\right)^2 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{13}$$

where $V_n(P, Q)$ is the n -th term of the Lucas sequence defined by the recurrence relation

$$V_0 = 2, \quad V_1 = P, \quad V_i = PV_{i-1} - QV_{i-2}, \quad i \geq 2. \tag{14}$$

Proof. The roots of $x^2 - Px + Q$ are $\alpha_1 = \frac{P - \sqrt{P^2 - 4Q}}{2}$, $\alpha_2 = \frac{P + \sqrt{P^2 - 4Q}}{2}$. Hence $R(x^2 - Px + Q, x^{q-1} - 1) = (\alpha_1 \alpha_2)^{q-1} - (\alpha_1^{q-1} + \alpha_2^{q-1}) + 1 = 1 + Q^{q-1} - V_{q-1}(P, Q)$.

Since we know $\left(\frac{P^2-4Q}{q}\right) = 1$ and $Q \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$, then the system of congruences $x^2 - Px + Q \equiv x^{q-1} - 1 \equiv 0 \pmod{q}$ has two solutions. So by Theorem 1 we have $1 + Q^{q-1} - V_{q-1}(P, Q) \equiv 0 \pmod{q^2}$, thus we get (12). Now using the identity $V_{2n}(P, Q) = V_n^2(P, Q) - 2Q^n$, we obtain (13). \square

Note that the congruences (12) and (13) are well-known [6, 8, 9], but here we give an alternative completely independent proof of these results.

Corollary 2. *Let q be an odd prime and k, P, Q be any integers such that $k^2 + Pk + Q \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$. If $\left(\frac{P^2-4Q}{q}\right) = 1$, then*

$$V_{q-1}(P + 2k, k^2 + Pk + Q) \equiv (k^2 + Pk + Q)^{q-1} + 1 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{15}$$

$$V_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2(P + 2k, k^2 + Pk + Q) \equiv \left((k^2 + Pk + Q)^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1\right)^2 \pmod{q^2}. \tag{16}$$

Proof. Since $(P + 2k)^2 - 4(k^2 + Pk + Q) = P^2 - 4Q$, this corollary follows from Theorem 4. \square

3.1. The Congruences Involving the Lucas Numbers

Let $P = 1, Q = -1$ and $\left(\frac{5}{q}\right) = 1$, i.e., by the Quadratic Reciprocity Law $q \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{5}$. Let an integer k satisfy $k^2 + k - 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$, then by Corollary 2

$$V_{q-1}(1 + 2k, k^2 + k - 1) \equiv (k^2 + k - 1)^{q-1} + 1 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{17}$$

$$V_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2(1 + 2k, k^2 + k - 1) \equiv (k^2 + k - 1)^{q-1} + 2(k^2 + k - 1)^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1 \pmod{q^2}. \tag{18}$$

If $k = 0$, then

$$L_{q-1} \equiv 2 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{19}$$

$$L_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2 \equiv 2 + 2(-1)^{\frac{q-1}{2}} \pmod{q^2}, \tag{20}$$

where L_n is the n -th Lucas number.

3.2. The Congruences Involving the Pell-Lucas Numbers

Let $P = 2, Q = -1$ and $\left(\frac{8}{q}\right) = 1$, i.e., by the Quadratic Reciprocity Law $q \equiv \pm 1 \pmod{8}$. Let an integer k satisfy $k^2 + 2k - 1 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{q}$, then by Corollary 2

$$V_{q-1}(2 + 2k, k^2 + 2k - 1) \equiv (k^2 + 2k - 1)^{q-1} + 1 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{21}$$

$$V_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2(2 + 2k, k^2 + 2k - 1) \equiv (k^2 + 2k - 1)^{q-1} + 2(k^2 + 2k - 1)^{\frac{q-1}{2}} + 1 \pmod{q^2}. \tag{22}$$

If $k = 0$, then

$$\tilde{P}_{q-1} \equiv 2 \pmod{q^2}, \tag{23}$$

$$\tilde{P}_{\frac{q-1}{2}}^2 \equiv 2 + 2(-1)^{\frac{q-1}{2}} \pmod{q^2}, \quad (24)$$

where \tilde{P}_n is the n -th Pell-Lucas number defined by:

$$\tilde{P}_0 = 2, \quad \tilde{P}_1 = 2, \quad \tilde{P}_i = 2\tilde{P}_{i-1} + \tilde{P}_{i-2}, \quad i \geq 2. \quad (25)$$

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